

Are we moving through outer space with a gamma factor of 1.0001?

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Abstract

The propose of this short article is the question if or not we are moving through space with an gamma factor of 1 or if we already have a different gamma factor. For this question the experimental masses of the electron and proton are compared to the theoretically derived values. For the calculation of the particle masses the newly derived resonance formula is used.

Introduction

If we want to use the resonance formula (according to ref [1]) to calculate the two elementary masses, which directly provide particle masses and are best known to us experimentally, then these two masses should be the electron mass at rest and the proton mass at rest. Doing so leads to the following values:

For better clarity, the quotients of the experimentally determined values and the theoretically calculated values are given here (the experimentally determined values are derived from the Particle Data Group).

$$\frac{0.5109989500015 \times 1E6}{2^{-1} 3^2 (3\pi)^4 \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\left(1 - \frac{1}{3\pi}\right)}}}}} \right)^4} = 1.0001055125 \quad m_{Ryd}$$

1.0001055125
for the electron

Analogously,

$$\frac{938.2720881629 \times 1E6}{2^0 3^{-2} (3\pi)^9 \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\sqrt{\left(1 - \frac{1}{3\pi}\right)}}}}} \right)^4} = 1.0001243394 \quad m_{Ryd}$$

1.0001243394
for the proton

Resonance formulas used to calculate the electron and proton masses are according to reference 1.

The results show that both particles have small discrepancies between the experimental and theoretical values, with a deviation of 0.1055 per thousand for the electron and 0.124 per thousand for the proton. Both particles are a little heavier in the experiment than in theory. This would correspond to a deviation factor of 1.0001055 for the electron and 1.000124 for the proton. Therefore, the experimentally determined mass of the two particles is a little larger than the theoretically calculated mass.

However, on Earth, we also move through outer space at considerable speed. Thus, this deviation factor could now correspond to an equally large gamma factor of around 1.001 for both elementary particles. However, contrary to the theory of relativity, this would correspond to a cumulative gamma factor. This means that the gamma factor is not 1 for a relative equilibrium of the movement of particles and measuring system. Instead, it corresponds to the joint movement with which the measuring system and particles move together through outer space.

According to this interpretation, the measured particle mass should be a little bit larger than the theoretically calculated particle mass. A gamma factor of 1.0001 would be very consistent with the astronomically calculated speed of the earth through outer space. Contrary to the theory of relativity, the gamma factor would then already be playing a role in the determination of the so-called "rest mass" of the elementary particles and is not automatically 1. This would also have a great advantage in that the paradoxes and irritations of the theory of relativity all disappear in one fell swoop.

If the gamma factor of a moving particle increases with movement, regardless of the movement of the observer, then it is always clear which particle is in motion and which is at rest. This also clarifies the particles for which lengths are shortened and time passes more slowly. Paradoxes as we know them from relativity do not arise.

References

1.) Arne B. Oscillations and Potentials of Mesons and Baryons submitted to Physics Essays.